

Kinetics of Propionylation of Cellulose with 2,2-Dichloropropionic Acid

RAJESH K. JAIN, KRISHAN LAL and HARI L. BHATNAGAR

Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 1 February 1980, accepted 19 May 1980

The reaction of cellulose with 2,2-dichloropropionic acid in chlorobenzene solvent in the presence of strong perchloric acid catalyst has been investigated as a function of time and temperature (30-60°). The reaction has been regarded to be taking place via the well-known AAC³ mechanism. The products were characterized by elemental analysis and spectral techniques. The degree of substitution, *p*, in each prepared sample has been determined and assuming a second order reaction, the specific rate constants were calculated. With the help of the derived data, the enthalpy, the entropy and the free energy of activation have been obtained and interpreted.

A large number of cellulose derivatives has been synthesized^{1,2,3}, including esters of inorganic and organic acids (apart from xanthate esters), ethers and graft co-polymers, although relatively few have achieved commercial importance. Organic esters are much more important at the present time. Malm and his co-workers⁴ have prepared the whole series of cellulose esters from acetate to stearate by reaction of the free acid at 60-65° in the presence of impelling agent (chloroacetic anhydride) and a catalyst. In addition to this general method, there is another one which may be used, namely, the action of acid chlorides in the presence of a base, especially pyridine^{5,6} or quinoline⁷. The cellulose acetates of varying degrees of substitution are prepared by first treating cellulose with acetic acid, then with acetic anhydride and a mineral acid catalyst. The fully acetylated product is subsequently reacted with water to achieve the desired degree of substitution. Cellulose propionate and cellulose butyrate, or, more commercially, acetate-propionate and acetate-butyrate mixtures are the only other commercially important cellulose esters. The mixed esters are generally more soluble and have better impact resistance than cellulose acetate. Esterification of cellulose with halogen-substituted acids provides an additional advantage as it has been observed that certain elements like nitrogen and halogens when incorporated into the matrix of cellulose impart flame resistance to it. In the following, a kinetic study of esterification of cellulose with 2,2-dichloropropionic acid has been described and the data analysed. So far no kinetic studies have been reported to date in spite of the potentialities of the reaction in flame proofing of cellulose⁸

Experimental

Reagents :

(i) *Cellulose* : The cellulose used was supplied by M/S. Dassel, West Germany. It was also dried over anhydrous calcium chloride under vacuum.

(ii) *Chlorobenzene* : The chemical used was supplied by M/S. Sarabhai M. Chemicals, India. It was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled. The distillate at 132° was collected for use.

(iii) *2,2-Dichloropropionic acid* : It was supplied by M/S. Koch Light Laboratories, Ltd., Colbrook, Bucks, England and was used as such.

(iv) *Perchloric acid (60%)* : It was supplied by M/S. Riedel-De Haenag, Seelze, Hannover, Germany.

(v) *Sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and silver nitrate* : All were of A.R. grade.

Propionylation of Cellulose : Propionylation of cellulose with 2,2-dichloropropionic acid for the definite periods of time at various temperatures was carried out in a three-necked flask immersed in an oil thermostat (constancy $\pm 0.5^\circ$) and fitted with a water condenser having a guard tube at its open end and a mercury sealed stirrer. Each time, 1.62 g of dry cellulose powder was allowed to get swollen in 10 ml of chlorobenzene for one hour period at the temperature of the experiment in a flask before the start of the reaction. This was done to increase the reactivity of cellulose. 4.2896 g of 2,2-dichloropropionic acid was added in 35.4 ml of chlorobenzene and allowed to attain the temperature of the experiment, then transferred to the flask containing cellulose mixed with perchloric acid (about 8% on the weight of cellulose). Perchloric acid catalyst was used as it was reported to have greater catalytic activity than the phosphoric acid or hydroiodic acid⁹. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred and refluxed for a given period at a given temperature. The medium was heterogeneous throughout the reaction period. The product was filtered through G-4 sintered glass funnel, washed thoroughly with distilled water, dried first in air

and then over P₂O₅ under vacuum. The samples of dichloropropionylated cellulose were stored in vacuum desiccator containing P₂O₅ as they were found to be highly hygroscopic.

The chlorine in the samples was estimated by the Carius method. From the % of chlorine in the sample (x), the degree of substitution (p) of the various samples was calculated using the equation^{1b},

$$p = \frac{162x}{100 \times 142.98 - 124.98x} \quad \dots (1)$$

where 162 and 142.98 are the molecular weights of anhydroglucose unit and 2,2-dichloropropionic acid respectively and 124.98 is the net increase in the molecular weight of cellulose resulting from the introduction of one substituent (CH₃CCl₂CO-) in one anhydroglucose unit.

Spectral Studies :

Infrared spectra of the samples in KBr pellets were obtained using Beckmann spectrophotometer, Model IR-20 (USA). Each sample (0.5-1.0 mg) was intimately mixed with 100 mg of dry powdered potassium bromide and its infrared spectra recorded.

The NMR spectra of acetone soluble part of the treated cellulose sample in DMSO-d₆ solution was recorded using Perkin-Elmer R-32, 90 MHz Spectrophotometer (U.K.). The chemical shifts were expressed in ppm downfield from TMS.

Theoretical considerations :

The reaction of cellulose with 2,2-dichloropropionic acid was throughout heterogeneous in nature. Under such conditions, all the hydroxyl groups in the anhydroglucose unit could be assumed to have the same reactivity¹⁰. This is an over simplification and probably only the primary -OH groups have the same reactivity irrespective of the chain length. Now, if the concept of equal reactivity of all the functional groups (-OH) irrespective of the size of polymer molecule¹¹ was assumed, then for a second order reaction, the rate equation can be formulated as,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{OH}] = k_r [\text{COOH in I}] [\text{OH in II}], \dots (2)$$

In order to eliminate the difficulties of writing a separate equation for the reaction for each hydroxyl group of cellulose with 2,2-dichloropropionic acid,

it was assumed that rate constant k_r was the same for all hydroxyl groups and did not change as the average molecular weight of cellulose increased.

Anhydroglucose units in the form of cellulose and 2,2-dichloropropionic acid were taken in the molar ratio 1 : 3 so that the initial molar concentration of the -OH groups of cellulose was the same as that of -COOH groups of 2,2-dichloropropionic acid (0.75M). Thus, if 'C₀' was the initial concentration of -OH groups of cellulose and 'C' was the concentration of the -OH groups at any time, t, the two may be related by the expression,

$$C = (1 - p')C_0, \quad \dots (3)$$

where, p', represented the extent of the reaction or the fraction of the hydroxyl groups initially present that had undergone reaction in a given time 't'.

Let, p, the degree of substitution, represent the average number of molecules of 2, 2-dichloropropionic acid combined with each anhydroglucose unit having molecular formula C₆H₇O₂(OH)₃. Under these considerations, equation (2) may be rewritten as

$$k_r = \frac{p}{C_0(3-p)t}, \quad \dots (4)$$

Thus, a plot of p/(3-p) versus 't' would give a straight line passing through the origin and having slope equal to C₀k_r. The specific reaction rate constant k_r can be calculated using the experimental value of the slope.

Results and Discussion

An important evidence for the reaction mechanism is to identify the products formed. All the solid products formed were identified by elemental analysis, infrared and NMR techniques. For spectral studies, it was found desirable to study the IR and NMR spectra of single components separately and compare the same with the spectra obtained on systems consisting of combination of the compounds.

The Infrared spectra of the treated sample exhibited strong carbonyl (1740 cm⁻¹) absorption bands due to stretching vibration of C=O bond in the ester group. A relative decrease in the intensity of hydroxyl band at 3600 cm⁻¹ was also observed. The presence of the band at 1110 cm⁻¹ in the prepared samples was believed to be associated with the pyranole ring motion in the amorphous cellulose. The acetone soluble part of the propionylated products showed strong IR absorption peak at about 650 cm⁻¹. The spectra indicated the presence of chloropropionylated cellulose as well as amorphous cellulose. The various frequencies bands of the reactants and products are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS OF CELLULOSE, 2,2-DICHLOROPROPIONIC ACID AND DICHLOROPROPIONYLATED CELLULOSE

(IR bands in cm^{-1})			
Cellulose	2,2 Dichloro- propionic Acid	Dichloropropio- nylated Cellulose	Band characteriza- tion (assignment)
3300-3600	—	3300-3600	O—H stretching
2900	—	2900	C—H stretching
—	1740	1740	C=O stretching in ester group
1640	—	1640	H—O—H stretching
1440	1440	1440	CH_2 bending
1380, 1320	—	1380, 1320	O—H bending
1110	1110	1110	C—OH stretching
1050	—	1050	Cellulose
900	—	900	Amorphous cellulose

The formation of cellulose 2, 2-dichloropropionate has been further established by comparing its 90 MHz NMR spectrum (Fig. 1) with that of commercial cellulose acetate. The typical $-\text{CH}_3$ proton signal which shows up at δ 2.08 in the case of commercial cellulose acetate showed a downfield shift in this product, appearing at δ 2.35 which can be attributed to the deshielding effect of the chlorine atoms on the neighbouring carbon atom. In addition, the signal in the range of δ 10.8- δ 11.8 (1H, $-\text{COOH}$) was also found to be absent in the product.

Fig. 1. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra of 2, 2-Dichloropropionylated Cellulose.

The present system follows a mathematical discipline of second order, which rules out the operation of unimolecular A_{AC}^1 and A_{AL}^1 mechanisms^{12,13}. As the reaction has been carried out under the conditions that are very similar to a typical acid-catalyzed esterification, it can be regarded to be taking place *via* the well known A_{AC}^2 mechanism. It is well known that the esterifications taking place by A_{AC}^2 mechanism are reversible, it becomes necessary to remove water from the medium if this is to be used as a preparative method for the formation of the ester. During the present investigations, nitrogen gas was passed into the reaction mixture in order to remove the water formed.

The percentage of chlorine in the products prepared after different intervals of time at various temperatures were estimated gravimetrically and the

degree of substitution in each treated sample was calculated using equation (1) and has been listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DEGREE OF SUBSTITUTION OF THE TREATED CELLULOSE SAMPLES AS A FUNCTION OF TIME

Time in hours	% Cl	% Combined $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{COOH}$	Degree of Substitution (p)	p (3-p)
Temperature 30°C				
0.5	0.1571	0.3164	0.0036	0.0012
1.0	0.2724	0.5485	0.0062	0.0021
1.5	0.4131	0.8319	0.0095	0.0032
2.0	0.5569	1.1214	0.0128	0.0043
2.5	0.6787	1.3667	0.0157	0.0053
3.0	0.8085	1.6281	0.0187	0.0063
3.5	0.9105	1.8335	0.0211	0.0071
4.0	1.0520	2.1185	0.0245	0.0082
Temperature 40°C				
0.5	0.1702	0.3427	0.0039	0.0013
1.0	0.3343	0.6732	0.0077	0.0026
1.5	0.4852	0.9771	0.0112	0.0037
2.0	0.6503	1.3096	0.0150	0.0050
2.5	0.8156	1.6425	0.0189	0.0063
3.0	1.0032	2.0202	0.0233	0.0078
3.5	1.1563	2.3285	0.0269	0.0091
4.0	1.3143	2.6467	0.0307	0.0103
Temperature 50°C				
0.5	0.2126	0.4281	0.0049	0.0017
1.0	0.3928	0.7910	0.0090	0.0030
1.5	0.5704	1.1487	0.0131	0.0044
2.0	0.7551	1.5206	0.0175	0.0059
2.5	0.9607	1.9346	0.0223	0.0075
3.0	1.1467	2.3092	0.0267	0.0090
3.5	1.3252	2.6687	0.0309	0.0104
4.0	1.5104	3.0416	0.0354	0.0119
Temperature 60°C				
0.5	0.2881	0.5802	0.0066	0.0022
1.0	0.4601	0.9265	0.0106	0.0035
1.5	0.6864	1.3822	0.0158	0.0053
2.0	0.9059	1.8243	0.0210	0.0071
2.5	1.0742	2.1632	0.0250	0.0084
3.0	1.3320	2.6824	0.0311	0.0105
3.5	1.5758	3.1733	0.0370	0.0125
4.0	1.6811	3.3854	0.0395	0.0134

Values of k_r as calculated by least squares method at different temperatures are: 30°C, 9.3×10^{-7} ; 40°C, 12.1×10^{-7} ; 50°C, 13.7×10^{-7} ; and 60°C, $15.4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

The plots of $p/(3-p)$ versus time for the various systems are shown in Fig. 2. These plots were found to be linear. The average value of the specific reaction rate k_r were determined by the method of least squares.

In order to calculate the energy of activation for this process, different values of $\ln k_r$ obtained at the various temperatures were plotted against. The method of least squares was used to evaluate the experimental energy of activation and the frequency factor A. The value of ΔE_{exp} and A were found to be 13.7 kJ mol^{-1} and $4.5 \times 10^8 \text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of Temperature on the Reaction of Cellulose with 2, 2-Dichloropropionic acid

The value of entropy of activation for the reaction was calculated from the equation $A = (ekT/h) e^{\Delta S^*/R}$. At 318.16 K, the average temperature of the experiment, the value of ΔS^* was found to be $-183.8 \text{ J deg}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The value of ΔH^* and ΔG^* were found to be 11.1 kJ mol^{-1} and 69.6 kJ mol^{-1} respectively.

The qualitative explanation of the negative entropy of activation can be given as follows. The formation of an activated complex from reactant molecules is accompanied by the conversion of translational-like and rotational-like degrees of freedom of the reactants to vibrational degrees of freedom of transition state species. The more widely spaced energy level for the latter type of molecular motion imply smaller entropy and thus the negative value of ΔS^* . A decrease in the value of ΔS^* ($-183.8 \text{ J deg}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in the system cellulose—2, 2-dichloropropionic acid conforms to the above explanation.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to the United States Department of Agriculture, Eastern Agriculture Research Service, for supporting the research under the grant No. FG-In-524, Project No. UR-A7-(20)-219 of research fellowship to R. K. J. Thanks are also due to Dr. I. S. Gur and Dr. R. P. Kapoor of this Department for useful suggestions in the present work.

References

1. E. ORT, H. M. SPURLIN and M. W. GRAFFLIN, Eds., "Cellulose and Cellulose Derivatives", 2nd Ed., Part II, Wiley-Interscience, New York 1954; (a) Chapter IX, (b) p. 1422.
2. E. M. FETTS, Ed., "Chemical Reactions of Polymers", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1964; (a) K. WARD, Jr. and A. J. MORAK, Chapter V; (b) M. G. GAYLORD and F. S. ANG, Chapter X, (c) W. A. REEVES and J. D. GUTHRIE, Chapter XVI, (d) R. E. WHITFIELD and W. L. WASLEY, Chapter VI.
3. B. G. RANBY and S. A. RYDHOLM, "Polymer Process", C. E. SCHILDKNECHT, Ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1956, Chapter IX.
4. H. T. CLARKE and C. J. MALM, *U. S. Patent*, 1,880,808 (to Eastman Kodak Co.), Jan. 8, 1929; *C. A.*, 1929, **23**, 1267.
5. M. HAGEDORN and P. MÖLLER, *Cellulosechemie*, 1931, **12**, 29; *C. A.*, 1931, **25**, 5982.
6. C. J. MALM, J. W. MENCH, D. L. KENDALL and G. D. HIATT, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1951, **43**, 684.
7. H. PRINGSHEIM, E. LORAND and K. WARD, Jr., *Cellulosechemie*, 1932, **13**, 119; *C. A.*, 1932, **26**, 6123.
8. R. K. JAIN, S. BHATNAGAR, K. LAL and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in Press).
9. V. M. VASIL'EV and V. I. SHAROV (USSR), *Khim. Tekhnol. Proizvod. Tselyyat*, 1971, 53 (Russ); *C. A.*, 1973, **78**, 138115h.
10. N. K. PYTAKINA, YU. V. MOISEEV and G. E. ZAIKOV, *Vysokomol. Soedin*, Ser. A, 1975, **17**(7), 1493; *C. A.*, 1975, **83**, 149349s.
11. P. J. FLORY, "Principles of Polymer Chemistry", Cornell University Press, New York, 1953.
12. C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Bell, London, 1953, Chapter XIV.
13. S. D. HAMANN, D. H. SOLOMAN and J. D. SWIFT, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1968, **A2**, 153.
14. W. L. BARNETT, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.* (London), 1921, **40**, 253T; *C. A.*, 1922, **16**, 341.